

EFFECTIVENESS OF A CLINICALLY IMMUNOLOGICALLY-ORIENTED ALGORITHM AND IMMUNO-CORRECTIVE THERAPY IN THE TREATMENT OF ACUTE ADHESIVE INTESTINAL INHERENCY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17937728>

Research objective. Assess the clinical effectiveness of a clinical-immunologically oriented treatment and diagnostic algorithm and immunocorrective therapy in patients with acute adhesive small intestinal obstruction.

Materials and methods. The study included 115 patients with acute adhesive intestinal obstruction. Depending on the treatment tactics used, patients were divided into two groups: control group (n=56) - treatment according to the standard protocol without immunological stratification; main group (n=59) - treatment using the developed clinical-immunologically-oriented algorithm and immunocorrective therapy. The algorithm provided for early assessment of the immune status (CD4+, CD8+, CD4/CD8 index, HLA-DR+, levels of IL-6, TNF- α , circulating immune complexes) and differentiated prescription of immunocorrective drugs depending on the severity of immune disorders. The frequency of postoperative complications, repeated surgical interventions, hospitalization duration, mortality, and the dynamics of immunological indicators were assessed.

Research results. The use of a clinical-immunologically-oriented algorithm led to a significant improvement in the clinical outcome of treatment. In the main group, the frequency of severe postoperative complications (III-V degrees) decreased by more than 2 times compared to the control group. The frequency of repeated surgical interventions decreased from 22.8% to 7.1%, and the average duration of hospitalization was reduced by 4 days. The most significant result was a decrease in mortality from 30.4% in the control group to 9.1% in the main group, which indicates a pronounced clinical effect of integrating immunological stratification and immunocorrective therapy. Immunological monitoring showed that clinical improvement was accompanied by normalization of cellular and humoral immunity indicators. A significant increase in the level of CD4+ T-lymphocytes, a restoration of the CD4/CD8 index, and an increase in HLA-DR+ expression, as well as a significant decrease in the levels of IL-6, TNF- α , and circulating immune complexes, was noted, reflecting a decrease in the systemic inflammatory response.

Conclusion. The use of a clinical and immunologically oriented algorithm and immunocorrective therapy for acute adhesive small intestinal obstruction significantly improves treatment outcomes, reduces the frequency of severe complications and mortality, and accelerates patient recovery. Early immune stratification and targeted immunotherapy are pathogenetically justified and promising directions in the comprehensive treatment of PCOS.